

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

New skills on innovation and digital innovation in curatorial professions, museum guides and landscape valorization

SPOKE N 3 – Tourism and culture industry

FP CIRIL - Cultural-Industry Regeneration Immersive Lab

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.

Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

1. Introduction

1.1 CIRIL and digital skills

As part of the NODES ecosystem, the CIRIL Flagship Project examines the ongoing digital shift within the cultural sector. A core objective of this work is defining the *"New skills on innovation and digital innovation in curatorial professions, museum guides and landscape valorization."*

The integration of tools like virtual reality and digital twins is reshaping how professionals approach curation and territory promotion. Consequently, the project seeks to verify the specific competencies required to blend traditional heritage management with digital storytelling and virtual accessibility.

This report outlines findings discussed during two recent scientific meetings:

1. **Biella (May 2025) – "Paesaggi narrativi: il biellese tra lingua, storia, estetica e media"**: This event focused on the Biella region, exploring how narrative techniques and media can serve as effective tools for promoting the local landscape and its industrial history.
2. **Turin (June 2025) – "Archivi e memoria, fonti e patrimonio culturale"**: This conference compared different research experiences, specifically looking at how archival sources can be used to generate new value for cultural assets.

The abstracts included below summarize the contributions from these sessions, illustrating the practical intersection of historical expertise and digital innovation.

2. Paesaggi narrativi: il biellese tra lingua, storia, estetica e media – BIELLA

2.1 Introduction

As part of Spoke 3, "Tourism and Culture Industry," the *Paesaggi narrativi* (Narrative Landscapes) conference examined the various ways the Biella landscape has been portrayed—historically and currently—through the lenses of language, aesthetics, and media.

With its diverse natural environment, rich cultural history, and deep industrial roots, the Biella region offers a perfect case study for the challenges of post-industrial reinvention. Adopting an interdisciplinary approach, the conference explored how storytelling can serve as a tool to enhance the territory and build community.

Operating within the NODES project—which fosters inclusive growth via digital and ecological transition—the event strengthened the dialogue between researchers, cultural figures, and local actors. The initiative aimed to showcase the scientific and cultural work of the University of Turin's team within Spoke 3, while serving as a meeting point for scholars, stakeholders, and local citizens to discuss how heritage drives innovation and sustainable development.

2.2 Abstracts

Matteo Rivoira and Guido Canepa - *Il paesaggio linguistico del Biellese nei materiali del Dizionario Atlante delle Parlate Biellesi (DAPB)*

This contribution intends to present some initial surveys conducted on the important dialectological work of the *Dizionario-atlante delle parlate biellesi* (Dictionary-Atlas of Biellese Dialects), created over more than twenty years by Alfonso Sella and Corrado Grassi and currently preserved at the Sella Foundation Archive. The work collects an enormous amount of linguistic data from the entire Biella territory and is an important testimony for the study of the varieties that characterize the area. Through the analysis of sections and elements drawn from the DAPB, an attempt will be made to highlight some characteristics of the linguistic landscape surrounding the city of Biella. Furthermore, exploiting the lexical data collected in the DAPB regarding the arts and crafts of the Biella area, an attempt will be made to frame the study of the material in the perspective of its potential use in an (eco)museum key.

Elena Corniolo and Francesca Romana Gaja - *Narrare il paesaggio: percorsi digitali per la valorizzazione dei beni storici e storico-artistici*

The intervention intends to present the potential of the experimental platform *Historygraphia* (POC-Nodes), a historical-digital atlas of cultural heritage for the construction of local narratives of a historical and historical-artistic nature, and its possible effects on local communities. So far, the project has involved two specific areas of the Western Alps—the Cuneo and Pinerolo areas—but its application can and hopefully intends to be extended to the entire subalpine region. The theme will be developed from a joint perspective, historical and historical-artistic, taking as examples some cases related to the Pinerolo valleys.

Laura Bonato - *Paesaggi ai margini: strategie e dinamiche relazionali in un'ottica di co-costruzione e progetti di tutela dell'ambiente*

In the last decades of the twentieth century, Alpine areas were witnesses to a notable process of depopulation: the effects on the environment caused by the abandonment of agro-pastoral practices extended beyond the local dimension, changing the characteristics of the landscape and cultural traditions, and transforming these areas into marginal lands. Research experiences gained in recent years in the field of Alpine anthropology have allowed for the observation of new landscapes generated by the actions and interventions of those involved in the phenomenon of neo-ruralism—people who have decided to move to the mountains, support a life project there, and invest in a sustainable economic system. The survey documents the existence of various realities that are trying to reintroduce different types of historically documented crops. These operations of revitalizing abandoned crops have a significant impact on the landscape: as has always been the case over the centuries, agricultural practices have shaped local communities, economies, cultures, and above all, the landscape itself. Local entrepreneurs and farms use the resources of their territories to increase the quality of life, operating with a view to sustainability, which translates specifically into the reconversion of marginal lands into productive areas: they reinvest in "natural capital," use the earth's resources responsibly, recover local ecotypes, limit environmental impact, and support action on the landscape.

Vera Gajju - «Le Guide» de Léon-Marius Manzetti: une écopoétique de la Vallée d'Aoste

Le Guide by Léon-Marius Manzetti, the "phoenix" of Valdostan literature in the French language, will be analyzed in this article from the perspective of eco-poetics. In particular, the focus will be on the literary and aesthetic component of the representation of places and the landscape as concepts of social and cultural valorization of the Valle d'Aosta territory. The aim is to demonstrate that this is not a work that arouses interest only at a local level or a typically regionalist work, but a work that addresses the world. Even if the boundaries in *Le Guide* are limited to a geographical and cultural space, this "francophone novel of the Valdostan Alps" shares a universal perspective and implements a reinvention of places and landscapes that are today increasingly unnoticed and from which we are increasingly distant.

Giovanni Casini - Da Ermenegildo alla Fondazione Zegna: episodi e forme di committenza imprenditoriale

Starting from the cycle of paintings commissioned in 1929-30 to Ettore Pistoletto Olivero for the Zegna Wool Mill in Trivero, inspired by the history of the Art of Wool, Ermenegildo Zegna began a journey of philanthropy and entrepreneurial patronage. This reflected his vision of shaping the mountain territory surrounding his company and its community. Beginning with an analysis of the representation of labor and the entrepreneurial model in Pistoletto's works, the intervention explores recent episodes like the "All'aperto" project. Through the current Fondazione Zegna, these initiatives foster a dialogue between artistic commissions, industry, landscape, and the local reality, touching on themes such as the environment and the relations between inhabitants and lived space.

Silvia Cavicchioli - Tra sviluppo territoriale e costruzione di un'identità nazionale. Quintino Sella organizzatore di cultura nel Biellese

This contribution examines the figure of Quintino Sella primarily as an organizer of culture and a promoter of significant development initiatives for the Biella territory. Nearly two hundred years after his birth, the study highlights the statesman's commitment to initiating the knowledge and valorization of territorial heritage in synergy with scientific research, the school system, and production apparatuses. It also demonstrates Sella's ability to promote a growth strategy that linked the local political base to the aspirations of the national ruling class.

Emanuela Locci - Il gruppo GFT, storie di donne e di tessuti

This intervention describes and analyzes the birth and development of the Gruppo Finanziario Tessile (GFT). Throughout its history, the group represented both the late 19th-century Biella textile industry and the dynamic Turinese reality where it developed from the 1930s onwards. Particular focus is placed on the condition of women within the Turin factory, where the destinies of women and textiles intertwine during the 20th century, encompassing labor struggles and progress.

Fabrizio Loreto - Alle origini della "strada della lana": un itinerario storico-turistico proposto da Franco Ramella

The intervention begins with an examination of an unpublished essay by historian Franco Ramella titled "Biella e le valli orientali di prima industrializzazione," written in the early 1980s. Originally commissioned by the Italian Touring Club, the essay was never published. The analysis of this essay and Ramella's broader work provides an opportunity for reflection on the "Strada della Lana" (Wool Road), a project developed by DocBi. This has evolved into a significant tourist itinerary revealing the link between history, industrial archaeology, art, culture, and landscape.

William Mazzaferro - I nodi della lana: le reazioni sindacali e padronali alla crisi del laniero biellese negli anni Sessanta e Settanta

This intervention seeks to reconstruct the various ways in which the crisis of the Biella wool sector was interpreted and the solutions proposed by opposing parties. By analyzing gray literature produced by employers' associations and trade unions during sample years between 1960 and 1980, the study highlights the primary interests present in the Biella area. The research observes conflicts between and within the union and entrepreneurial worlds. The evolution of these interests is linked to structural changes induced by the crisis that affected the Biella production fabric.

Andrea Strazzoni - Quintino Sella oltre la geologia: network tecnico-scientifici fra Biella e il Nord Europa

This intervention explores aspects of Quintino Sella's figure related to the history of science, specifically his contribution to technological innovation in the textile-wool industry through European contacts in Germany, England, and Belgium. Through an analysis of Sella's correspondence, the study aims to reconstruct the image of "Sella the scientist". While previously linked mainly to geology and mineralogy, this research highlights his vision of the relationship between national politics and science.

Paolo Furia - Il paesaggio biellese tra passato industriale e presente post-industriale

The industrial character is the typical, even prototypical, feature of the Biellese landscape, visible through textile factories, chimneys, worker villages, and water canals throughout the valleys and the city of Biella. The crisis of the textile sector has led to a profound transformation, turning the area into a post-industrial territory where abandoned factories exist alongside structures repurposed for services and creativity. This study observes how the concept of "industrial landscape" emerged as an aesthetic compensation for the loss of a functioning world, transforming what was once seen as a problematic byproduct of industrialization into a landscape heritage worthy of valorization. The analysis explores local audiovisual narratives that use the aesthetic experience of these factories to navigate a process of self-understanding between nostalgia, memory, and future perspective.

Maria Ida Bernabei - *Dai Dieci ai Sessanta. Il film d'impresa racconta il territorio*

This intervention focuses on the industrial landscape of Biella through the lens of corporate films, which document the development and crisis of the textile district across three historical periods. The first period (early 20th century to WWI) features scarce corporate production, with the territory's story largely found in family films. The second period coincides with the Fascist regime, characterized by propaganda newsreels and documentaries that celebrated local industrial progress as part of national modernization. The third period, from the post-war era to the economic boom, represents the peak of corporate film production. These films not only document the economic-cultural system but play a central role in constructing a territorial identity linked to industrial progress, showing the impact of modernization on the social fabric of the Biella area.

Alberto Spadafora - *Strategie di location placement audiovisivo nella rigenerazione sostenibile del territorio biellese*

This contribution proposes audiovisual strategies for a cultural project aimed at the sustainable regeneration of the Biella territory. By identifying recent social and environmental phenomena, the study aims to inspire authentic and updated narratives that promote ecological and social sustainability. Drawing from Tourism, Production, and Audiovisual Studies, the intervention suggests a shift in perception from "displacement" to "placement," turning the Biellese area from a mere place into a recognizable "location" and "destination." Through specific "pull" factors—such as the recognizability of places, the performativity of themes (like the textile sector), and the personality of key figures—audiovisual productions can foster a generative narrative that contributes to the renewal of the collective imagination and supports sustainable tourism.

3. Archivi e memoria, fonti e patrimonio culturale - TURIN

3.1 Introduction

As part of Spoke 3, "Tourism and Culture Industry," the conference "Archivi e memoria, fonti e patrimonio culturale. Esperienze di ricerca e valorizzazione a confronto." focused on the various practices aimed at promoting archival collections. The discussion centered on key themes such as historical and oral memory, the promotion of cultural and folk heritage, and the practice of returning materials to their original communities, particularly through the lenses of museum studies and sustainable tourism.

Archival sources serve as a cross-disciplinary research focus, bridging fields such as history, art history, linguistics, musicology, demo-ethno-anthropology, sociology, and ethnology. The conference brought together scholars from diverse academic backgrounds with representatives from the institutions responsible for the preservation of these materials.

In addition to introducing the scientific community to various archives and their unique characteristics, the event provided visibility to the stakeholders dedicated to source preservation. The ultimate goal was to foster new perspectives on the protection, promotion, and restitution of these materials. In doing so, the conference actively contributes to the valorization of local cultural heritage preserved within regional archives.

Overall, the event aimed to showcase the scientific and cultural research conducted by the University of Turin research group involved in Spoke 3 of the NODES project.

3.2 Abstracts

PARTE I: FONTI D'ARCHIVIO E RICERCA STORICA

Matteo D'Ambrosio - *Le interviste di Giorgina Levi. Fonti orali per la storia del movimento operaio*

The article describes the analytical cataloging and digitization project concerning the Sound Archive within the personal collection of Giorgina Arian Levi (1910-2011), held at the Fondazione Istituto piemontese Antonio Gramsci. Giorgina Levi was a politician, teacher, and a prolific historian and researcher of the working-class movement. The Sound Archive comprises 84 audio tracks, totaling 105 hours of recordings, collected by Levi during the 1970s and 1980s for her historical studies on the working-class movement, socialism, and social struggles in Piedmont.

Enrico Miletto - *Una voce al servizio del Partito. Radio Oggi in Italia, l'emittente cecoslovacca del Pci (1950-1970)*

Italy's transition from civil war to democracy was extremely complex. Militants and former communist partisans became the target of political trials instituted by a judiciary which, as a direct consequence of the failure to purge the system, had seen figures compromised by the previous regime remain in their posts. Accused of crimes committed during the war or in the period immediately following the conflict, some managed to flee to Czechoslovakia with the help of the Italian Communist Party. A small group was included in the editorial staff of Radio Oggi in Italia, a radio station that broadcast clandestinely from Prague, whose story, fully embedded in the context of the Cold War, is reconstructed in this article.

Emanuela Locci - *I fondi Mazzonis e GFT dell'Archivio di Stato di Torino. Per una storia al femminile del tessile piemontese*

The State Archives of Turin hold two collections that are very important for the history of the textile industry in Piedmont and, more generally, in Italy at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries: the Mazzonis collection and the Gruppo Tessile Industriale (GFT) collection. On this occasion, we intend to highlight the history and events related to the female workers who worked in both production facilities at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, through the sources consulted in this archive. Women have always represented the majority of the workforce, but their history and the contribution they made, for example in the struggles for workers' rights, especially at the turn of the century, has been little explored by historiography.

Enrico Lusso - *Fonti contabili bassomedievali e studio dell'architettura castellana nell'area alpina occidentale*

Beginning in the 13th century, the House of Savoy – much like other European ruling dynasties – undertook a reorganization of the administration of their territories through the establishment of districts called castellania: territorial units structured around a central castle and overseen by an appointed official. Among the various responsibilities of this official was the annual reporting of revenues and expenditures. Of particular interest within these records is the entry *opera castri*, referring to the section dedicated to works carried out on fortified structures within the administrative boundaries of the castellany. In most

cases, this section consists of a detailed itemization of expenses related to the procurement of materials, their transportation, and the wages of laborers involved in both routine maintenance and extraordinary works, as well as entirely new constructions. These documents make it possible not only to reconstruct with precision and specificity the material composition and spatial organization of many castles in the Western Alpine region – thereby offering a more authentic and less stereotyped understanding of these structures – but also to trace their development and transformations over the medium and long term.

Elena Corniolo - Quando la ricerca incontra il territorio: archivi, fonti e comunità nel Tardo Medioevo alpino

Drawing on insights offered by recent studies on Alpine communities in the late Middle Ages, this contribution seeks to advance several reflections on the challenges and opportunities that this context presents for historical research. Particular attention is devoted to the archival and documentary resources available to scholars investigating late-medieval Alpine communities, as well as to the importance of active collaboration between academia and local communities – both for conducting territorially grounded historical research and for ensuring effective public dissemination.

Francesca Romana Gaja - L'abbazia di Santa Maria a Pinerolo tra frammentazione delle fonti documentarie e sopravvivenza del patrimonio figurativo

The present contribution stems from research conducted jointly with Elena Corniolo on archival sources (pastoral visits, parish reports) relevant to reconstructing the figurative and cultural heritage of the Pinerolo area, with particular attention to Pellice and Chisone valleys, over a broad chronological span from the sixteenth to the eighteenth century. Over the course of this research, the case of the Abbey of Santa Maria in Pinerolo emerged as particularly significant, as it constituted a major center of ecclesiastical authority throughout the Piedmont region and part of Liguria. The complex events involving the abbey and its adjoining parish church from the seventeenth century onward led to the fragmentation and partial dispersal of their documentary heritage, which survives today in various locations. The surviving figurative heritage—most notably the altarpieces now housed in the parish church of San Verano—makes it possible to complement the information drawn from documentary sources, restoring an accurate memory of these sites and enriching our understanding of the historical and artistic heritage of the Pinerolo area.

PARTE II: ARCHIVI E RICERCA LINGUISTICA

Livio Gaeta, Dario Capelli, Caterina Saracco - Documentare e salvaguardare le minoranze walser: il ruolo delle piattaforme digitali

In this paper, we highlight two recently developed, technology-enabled platforms for documenting the small Walser varieties spoken in northwestern Italy. These platforms address the urgent need to record linguistic varieties that are undergoing rapid erosion. Through four case studies, we show that they also support fine-grained analysis, revealing structurally significant and original features shaped by centuries of language contact. Because they are readily available and easy to use, these digital resources can motivate speakers—especially younger generations—to engage with their heritage and help slow, or even halt, the dissolution threatening these “small languages”.

Théo Patrick Bielle, Elisabetta Carpitelli, Antonio Romano - L'esperienza di ricerca e valorizzazione dei dati dialettali del LFSAG: dati sociofonetici di Piemonte e Valle d'Aosta

At the LFSAG, oral data collection activities on Romance languages and dialects have been carried out for decades. In this line of research, the laboratory is currently involved in data digitisation activities within the framework of the DIGITALIA project and the Charter of Dialects of Italy. Recently, in collaboration with the Grenoble Dialectology Centre and the CNRS, SOPHOGEF was launched. SOPHOGEF is a transnational research project that aims to carry out a sociophonetic analysis of Francoprovençal, the most endangered of the Gallo-Romance varieties. Current activities include acoustic analysis of the collected oral data that confirm significant variation already described by the sources.

Daniela Mereu - Descrivere l'italiano regionale di Torino della seconda metà del Novecento: il ruolo degli archivi orali

This paper presents the research project "Oral archives for linguistic research: Turin Italian," which aims to study the evolution of the regional variety of Italian spoken in Turin, following the internal migrations that have affected the city since the second half of the last century. The data used in this first phase of the research are represented by the oral testimonies of Turin speakers born between the late 1800s and early 1900s, contained in the Giorgina Levi Collection and dating back to the 1970s and 1980s. This study provides an initial exploration of the sociolinguistic varieties found in the data collection under examination.

Valentina Sparviero - Il progetto A.D.e.L.A.I.D.e. (Archivio DigitalE Lascaris: Accesso, Indagini, Diffusione): lo studio linguistico e socio-linguistico su una lettera autografa

The object of this article is to introduce the A.D.e.L.A.I.D.e. project: one of the purposes is to scan and study the archival collections at the Cavour's Foundation that preserves autographs letters. In particular, the focus of this article is the analysis of a letter, conserved in one of the archives; first, will be discussed the writers' information and the introduction to the letter's digitalization, then will be illustrated the linguistic and sociolinguistic information that the study about this letter reveals.

PARTE III: ARCHIVI DEL PATRIMONIO POPOLARE E DELLA MEMORIA ORALE

Giulia Ferraris, Silvia Giordano - Dare voce: l'Archivio di Nuto Revelli fra memoria e valorizzazione

This contribution aims to present the activities and projects promoted by the Nuto Revelli Foundation regarding the conservation and enhancement of the Nuto Revelli archive. It presents an in-depth analysis of Revelli's sound archive and the project "Dare voce al Mondo dei vinti", which contains unpublished interviews conducted for the books 'Il mondo dei vinti. Testimonianze di vita contadina' (1977) and 'L'anello forte. La donna: storie di vita contadina' (1985).

Flavio Giacchero - Gli archivi del CREO: esperienze di restituzione sul territorio

The nature and purpose of CREO (Center for Research on Ethnomusic and Oral Tradition) lie primarily in the preservation and safeguarding of documents that represent memory and culture, and in their restitution through consultation as well as through their possible uses and reuses. This contribution aims to outline some of the strategies developed by CREO for the enhancement of its archives and to illustrate how these strategies may reverberate in the promotion of local territories, both in cultural and social terms, and in relation to their attractiveness.

Ilario Meandri, Giulia Ferdeghini, Lianna D'Amato - Acusteme: catalogazione, Linked Data e ontologie per il patrimonio etnomusicologico

The cataloguing of music documents can be challenging due to the partial adequacy of current descriptive models. The native Linked Open Data cataloguing system Acusteme, developed by the University of Turin, aims to optimize the description of music-research related resources, to improve data retrieval, and to enrich data. Its data model ensures a granular description of music resources and introduces specific metadata for materials deriving from ethnographic, ethnomusicological, and musicological research.

Laura Bonato - Fonti e scrittura etnografica: fatti e finzioni

Cultural anthropology can utilise literary sources as valuable tools for understanding cultural representations and symbolic practices of a given society. However, the use of these sources requires a series of methodological precautions to avoid distorted interpretations. Literature is not an objective document; it is an aesthetic and symbolic construction. It does not describe “facts” but representations, and should therefore be read as a “cultural discourse” rather than as a chronicle.

PARTE IV: VALORIZZAZIONE DELLE FONTI D'ARCHIVIO PER LA PROMOZIONE DEL TERRITORIO

Stefania Benetti, Stefania Cerutti - Catalizzatore di innovazione: TOEP come archivio digitale per progetti creativi

The contribution presents the TOEP (Tourism Open-ended Experimentation Platform) as an innovative digital infrastructure capable of integrating archiving, cultural valorisation, and the development of sustainable tourism experiences. The platform enables the collection, organisation, and sharing of creative projects, transforming them into active tourism experiences. The chapter also examines the educational and project outcomes of the 2024 and 2025 Challenges, innovative teaching initiatives based on co-creation and territorial experimentation.

Paolo Gheda, Paolo Perri - La riscoperta dell'Industrial Heritage nella Bassa Valle d'Aosta. Le fonti d'archivio tra promozione turistica e ricerca di un'identità particolare

This paper argues that primary sources are crucial not only for reconstructing the industrialisation of the Aosta Valley but also for reinterpreting its legacy. They allow the identification and valorisation of regional industrial heritage, opening new avenues for cultural tourism. The analysis of archival sources allows the development of new forms of tourist storytelling and the study of the social consequences of industrialisation, contributing to a fuller understanding of the Lower Valley's identity.

Sara Rivoira, Ilaria Testa - Archivi, comunità e territorio: dalla conoscenza alla valorizzazione. L'Esperienza della digital library del patrimonio culturale metodista e valdese

Archives, territory, and community are closely interconnected, particularly in the case of the Waldensian and Methodist cultural heritage in Piedmont. To enhance this heritage means redefining methods used in cataloguing and implementing actions to involve the local community. The Historical Archives and Cultural Heritage Office of the Waldensian Church Board shares its experience in promoting cultural heritage using new technologies.

Laura Facchin, Massimiliano Ferrario - Emilio Alemagna: tracce d'autore. L'archivio ritrovato e il progetto di valorizzazione

Count Emilio Alemagna (1833–1910) was a prominent figure in the architectural renewal of western Lombardy. The previously unpublished private archive now makes it possible to reconstruct his multifaceted career. This contribution presents an initial project for the reorganization of the documentary materials, with the objective of transforming his residence into a destination for guided visits and integrating it into broader regional itineraries.

Alessandra Casati - Archivi di seta. Nuove esplorazioni nel Fondo Filande e Tessiture Costa per una narrazione della produzione serica a Como come valore di comunità

The paper presents the first results of a historical survey of silk production in Como in the 20th century. Business archives make it possible to investigate the organizational modes of production processes and the division of labour. The main example is offered by the archives of Filande e Tessiture Costa, which had important collaborations with fashion maisons such as Dior, Givenchy, and Max Mara.

4. ANNEXES

CONVEGNO DI STUDI PAESAGGI NARRATIVI

Il Biellese tra lingua, storia,
estetica e media

16-17 maggio
2025

Città Studi
Corso G. Pella, 2 Biella

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PROGRAMMA

VENERDÌ 16 MAGGIO 2025

9.00

Saluti istituzionali

9.30-11.15

Sistema creativo e territorio. Il modello biellese

Tavola rotonda

Chair: **Giulia Carluccio, Silvia Cavicchioli** (Università di Torino)

Michele Cerruti But (Cittadellarte – Fondazione Pistoletto)
Francesca Gambetta (Fondazione Compagnia di San Paolo)
Alberto Panzanelli (Fondazione Cassa di Risparmio di Biella)
Andrea Polidori (Osservatorio del Biellese Beni Culturali & Paesaggio)
Angelica Sella (Fondazione Sella onlus)

11.15

Coffee break

11.30-13.00

L'immagine del Biellese. Estetiche, media, audiovisivi

Parte I

Chair: **Giulia Carluccio** (Università di Torino)
Discussant: **Silvio Alovisio** (Università di Torino)

Il paesaggio biellese tra passato industriale e presente post-industriale

Paolo Furia (Università di Torino)

Dai Dieci ai Sessanta. Film, impresa e racconto del territorio
Maria Ida Bernabei (Università di Torino)

Strategie di location placement audiovisivo per la rigenerazione sostenibile del territorio biellese

Alberto Spadafora (Università di Torino)

13.00

Light lunch

14.30-18.30

Paesaggi narrati nelle Alpi occidentali. Tra storia, antropologia, storia dell'arte, linguistica e letteratura

Keynote lecture: **Egidio Dansero** (Università di Torino)

Paesaggio industriale e patrimonio territoriale: trama e ordito per geografie della transizione

Discussant: **Laura Bonato** (Università di Torino)

15.45

Coffee break

16.00

Chair: **Egidio Dansero** (Università di Torino)

Discussant: **Andrea Del Duca** (Direttore dell'Ecomuseo del Lago d'Orta e Mottarone)

Il paesaggio linguistico del Biellese nei materiali del Dizionario Atlante delle Parlate Biellesi (DAPB)

Matteo Rivoira e Guido Canepa (Università di Torino)

Narrare il paesaggio: percorsi digitali per la valorizzazione dei beni storici e storico-artistici

Elena Corniolo, Francesca Romana Gaja, Aurora Laurenti (Università di Torino)

Paesaggi ai margini: strategie e dinamiche relazionali in un'ottica di co-costruzione e progetti di tutela dell'ambiente
Laura Bonato (Università di Torino)

Ecopoetica del paesaggio piemontese e valdostano nell'arte e nella letteratura del XX secolo

Vera Gajiu (Università di Torino)

18.30-20.30

Proiezione del docufilm di **Maurizio Pellegrini** *E noi zitti?*

Graffiti sparsi sulla Pettinature Rivetti di Biella (2024),

Produzione Video Astolfo sulla Luna, in presenza dell'autore

20.30

Cena - Palazzo Ferrero, Biella

SABATO 17 MAGGIO 2025

9.00-13.00

L'immagine del Biellese. Estetiche, media, audiovisivi

Parte II

Keynote lecture: **Paolo D'Angelo** (Università di Roma Tre)
Paesaggio e giardino: due falsi amici?

Chair: **Giulia Carluccio** (Università di Torino)

Discussant: **Chiara Simonigh** (Università di Torino)

10.30

Coffee break

10.45

Visita al giardino di Palazzo La Marmora

13.00

Light lunch

14.30-18.15

Lavoro, impresa e scienza nel Biellese tra Ottocento e Novecento

Keynote lecture: **Claudio Dellavalle** (Università di Torino)
Note sul distretto laniero biellese: trasformazioni produttive, mutazioni culturali e dinamiche politiche

Chair: **Silvia Cavicchioli** (Università di Torino)

Discussant: **Danilo Craveia** (Rete Archivi Biellesi)

Quintino Sella oltre la geologia: network tecnico-scientifici fra Biella e il Nord Europa

Andrea Strazzone (Università di Torino)

Il gruppo GFT, storie di donne e di tessuti

Emanuela Locci (Università di Torino)

I nodi della lana: le reazioni sindacali e padronali alla crisi del laniero biellese negli anni Sessanta

William Mazzaferro (Università di Torino)

16.30

Coffee Break

16.45

Alle origini della “strada della lana”: un itinerario storico-turistico proposto da Franco Ramella

Fabrizio Loreto (Università di Torino)

La storia dell’Arte della Lana secondo Ermenegildo Zegna ed Ettore Pistoletto Olivero

Giovanni Casini (Università di Torino)

18.30

Conclusioni e chiusura lavori

COMITATO SCIENTIFICO-ORGANIZZATIVO

Maria Ida Bernabei, Marco Biolatti, Laura Bonato, Guido Canepa, Giulia Carluccio, Giovanni Casini, Silvia Cavicchioli, Elena Corniolo, Gianluca Cuniberti, Paolo Furia, Francesca Romana Gaja, Vera Gajiu, Aurora Laurenti, Emanuela Locci, Fabrizio Loreto, William Mazzaferro, Matteo Rivoira, Piercarlo Rossi, Chiara Simonigh, Alberto Spadafora, Andrea Strazzoni

Convegno realizzato nell’ambito del progetto NODES finanziato dal MUR su fondi M4C2, Investimento 1.5, Avviso “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, del PNRR finanziato dall’Unione Europea NextGenerationEU (Grant agreement Cod. n. ECS000036)
<https://www.ecs-nodes.eu/>

VENERDÌ 20 GIUGNO
Complesso Aldo Moro
Sala Lauree
Via Giuseppe Verdi, 41, TO

Esperienze di valorizzazione delle fonti d'archivio per la promozione del territorio

Keynote speakers:

14:30 Stefania Cerutti, Stefania Benetti (Università del Piemonte Orientale)

Catalizzatore di innovazione: TOEP come archivio digitale per progetti creativi

15:15 Alberto Spadafora (Università di Torino)

Database in prospettiva. Il sistema audiovisivo biellese nel portale della Film Commission Torino Piemonte

15:45 Paolo Gheda, Paolo Perri (Università della Valle d'Aosta)

Riscoperta e valorizzazione dell'Industrial Heritage nella Bassa Valle d'Aosta. Le fonti d'archivio tra promozione turistica e ricerca di un'identità particolare

Pausa caffè

16:30 Sara Rivoira, Ilaria Testa (Ufficio Archivio Storico e Beni Culturali Tavola Valdese)

Archivi, comunità e territorio: dalla conoscenza alla valorizzazione. L'esperienza della digital library del patrimonio culturale metodista e valdese

17:00 Laura Facchin, Massimiliano Ferrario (Università dell'Insubria)

Emilio Alemagna: tracce d'autore. L'archivio ritrovato e il progetto di valorizzazione

17:30 Alessandra Casati (Università dell'Insubria)

Archivi di seta. Nuove esplorazioni nel Fondo Filande e Tessiture Costa per una narrazione della produzione serica a Como come valore di comunità

Conclusioni e saluti

Comitato scientifico e organizzativo:

Laura Bonato, Guido Canepa, Massimo Cerruti,
Elena Corniolo, Gianluca Cuniberti, Francesca
Romana Gaja, Agnes Garrone, Daniela Mereu,
Matteo Rivoira, Antonio Romano

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Organizzato da:

Dipartimento di
LINGUE
LETTERATURE STRANIERE
CULTURE MODERNE

Con il sostegno di:

Spoke 3
Industria
del turismo
e cultura

UNIVERSITÀ
DI TORINO

Questo convegno è realizzato nell'ambito del progetto
NODES, finanziato dal MUR sui fondi M4C2 -
Investimento 1.5 Avviso "Ecosistemi dell'Innovazione",
nell'ambito del PNRR finanziato dall'Unione europea -
NextGenerationEU (Grant agreement Cod.
n.ECS00000036)

Università di Torino

19-20 giugno 2025

Convegno di studi

Archivi e memoria, fonti e patrimonio culturale

Esperienze di ricerca
e valorizzazione a confronto

PROGRAMMA

GIOVEDÌ 19 GIUGNO
Palazzo Nuovo
Sala Lauree Terracini
Via Sant'Ottavio, 20, TO

VENERDÌ 20 GIUGNO
Complesso Aldo Moro
Sala Lauree
Via Giuseppe Verdi, 41, TO

Ore 9:00 Inizio del convegno

Saluti istituzionali

Marcella Costa (UniTo - direttrice LLSCM), **Paolo Cozzo** (UniTo - direttore Studi Storici), **Gianluca Cuniberti** (UniTo - Nodes), **Alessandro Mengozzi** (UniTo - direttore StudiUm), **Piercarlo Rossi** (UniTo - Nodes)

Fonti d'archivio e ricerca storica

Keynote speaker:

09:30 Alessandro Casellato (Università Ca' Foscari)

Archivi orali e ricerca storica: un ventaglio di opportunità

10:15 Matteo D'Ambrosio (Fondazione Istituto Gramsci)

Le interviste di Giorgina Arian Levi. Fonti orali per la storia del movimento operaio

10:45 Enrico Miletto (Università di Torino)

Una voce al servizio del Partito. Radio Oggi in Italia, l'emittente cecoslovacca del Pci (1950-1970)

Pausa caffè

11:30 Emanuela Locci (Università di Torino)

I fondi Mazzonis e GFT dell'Archivio di Stato di Torino. Per una storia al femminile del tessile piemontese

12:00 Enrico Lusso (Università di Torino)

Fonti contabili bassomedievali e studio dell'architettura castellana nell'area alpina occidentale

12:30 Elena Corniolo, Francesca Romana Gaja (Università di Torino)

Fonti per la conoscenza e la valorizzazione del patrimonio culturale nel contesto alpino occidentale (XV-XVIII secolo)

Pausa pranzo

Archivi e ricerca linguistica

Keynote speaker:

14:30 Silvia Calamai (Università di Siena)

Perché la linguistica non può ignorare gli archivi orali del passato?

15:15 Livio Gaeta, Dario Capelli (Università di Torino),

Caterina Saracco (Università di Milano)

Dal corpus al dizionario: la piattaforma CLiMALp e la salvaguardia delle minoranze walser

15:45 Théo Bielle, Elisabetta Carpitelli (Université Grenoble-Alpes),

Antonio Romano (Università di Torino)

L'esperienza di ricerca e valorizzazione dei dati dialettali del LFSAG: dati sociofonetici di Piemonte e Valle d'Aosta

Pausa caffè

16:30 Daniela Mereu (Università di Torino)

Descrivere l'italiano regionale di Torino della seconda metà del Novecento: il ruolo degli archivi orali

17:00 Paola Cifarelli, Valentina Sparviero (Università di Torino)

Il progetto A.D.e.L.A.I.D.e. (Archivio DigitalE Lascaris: Accesso, Indagini, DiffusionE)

17:30 Luca Bellone (Università di Torino)

Archivi epistolari: note linguistiche sulle lettere di Camillo Cavour (1815-1861)

Conclusioni

Ore 9:00 Inizio seconda giornata

Patrimonio popolare e memoria orale

Keynote speakers:

09:30 Piercarlo Grimaldi (Università di Scienze

Gastronomiche di Pollenzo), **Davide Porporato** (Università del Piemonte Orientale)

Dall'oralità al digitale: i Granai della Memoria

10:15 Beatrice Verri, Giulia Ferraris (Fondazione Nuto Revelli),

Silvia Giordano (Università di Torino)

Dare voce: l'Archivio di Nuto Revelli fra memoria e valorizzazione

10:45 Maria Ida Bernabei (Università di Torino)

Immagini dal tessile: archivi, film d'impresa e racconto del distretto industriale biellese

Pausa caffè

11:30 Flavio Giacchero (Centro Ricerca Etnomusica e Oralità)

Gli archivi del CREO: esperienze di restituzione sul territorio

12:00 Ilario Meandri, Giulia Ferdeghini, Lianna Flavia

D'Amato (Università di Torino)

Il sistema catalografico nativo LOD Acusteme: una soluzione innovativa al problema della catalogazione dei materiali di interesse etnomusicologico

12:30 Laura Bonato (Università di Torino)

Fonti e scrittura etnografica: fatti e finzioni

Pausa pranzo